

Joanna Rak

pp. 11–29 **Theorising Nation-State-Building Myths*
as an Explaining Factor**

**Teoretyzowanie mitów państwowotwórczych
jako czynnika wyjaśniającego**

Abstract

Keywords political myths, theory, theoretical category, explanatory framework
Based on a critical analysis of explanatory frameworks, the article aims to identify theoretical models treating nation-state-building myths as an explaining factor. In doing so, it reveals an explanatory potential of this theoretical category and facilitates the selection of political myths as a theoretical grounding of empirical analysis. It shows the variety of possible ways of theorising political myths. Moreover, it aims to determine their correctness and applicability to empirical studies. The analyses contribute to studies on myths by exposing the strengths and limitations of selected explanatory models. Finally, they uncover possible scopes and directions for developing the current models.

Streszczenie

Słowa klucze mity polityczne, teoria, kategoria teoretyczna, model eksplanacyjny
Artykuł ma na celu zidentyfikowanie, na podstawie krytycznej analizy schematów eksplanacyjnych, modeli teoretycznych traktujących mity państwowotwórcze jako czynnik wyjaśniający. Określa on potencjał eksplanacyjny tej kategorii teoretycznej oraz możliwości związane z wyborem mitów politycznych jako podstawy teoretycznej analizy empirycznej. Ukazuje różnorodność sposobów teoretyzowania mitów politycznych. Ponadto ma na celu ustalenie poziomu poprawności i stosowalności podejść teoretycznych do badań empirycznych. Wyniki analizy są wkładem do badań nad mitami, bo wykazują mocne strony i ograniczenia wybranych modeli wyjaśniających. Wyznaczają również możliwe zakresy oraz kierunki rozwoju ujęć teoretycznych.

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Introduction

According to the most cited definition of a political myth, it is “an ideologically marked narrative which purports to give a true account of a set of past, present, or predicted political events and which is accepted as valid in its essentials by a social group.”¹ It rests upon an assumption that political myths always use a group of people as a protagonist or a frame of reference and tackle politically relevant issues, which is a commonly shared premise in the subject literature.² As “enduring identity narratives,”³ all political myths are or can act as nation-state-building myths, even though their functions in these processes differ,⁴ when established and cultivated within a nation-state community.⁵ In this article, the theoretical categories of political myths and nation-state-building myths are treated as having a common semantic field when applied to a nation-state community. Hence, these categories will be used interchangeably as synonyms for the article’s purposes. It is a simplification that should be kept in mind when reading the article because not always and not all political myths are nation-state-building in a general approach.⁶

Despite always being socially important, never have political myths been in the mainstream of social sciences.⁷ More frequently, they were in the spotlight of philosophers who reflected on their nature and links to philosophy.⁸ What is more, they were under-evaluated as not being in the hardcore of quantitative comparative politics,⁹ as evidenced by the share of articles on myths in the flagship journals of international scientific associations grouping social science researchers (e.g., *The International Political Science Review*, the journal of the International Political Science Association). They also suffered a decline as a research subject for the students of political thought and communication until the great economic crisis of 2007–2008.¹⁰ The latter inspired the resurgence of

¹ Ch. Flood, *Political Myth*, London–New York: Routledge, 2001, p. 44.

² J.C. Morgan, *The Partido Liberacion Nacional of Costa Rica: A Case Study on Political Myth and Political Culture*, Louisiana: Louisiana State University and Agricultural & Mechanical College, 1979, p. 79; L. Dittmer, “Political Culture and Political Symbolism: Toward a Theoretical Synthesis,” *World Politics* 1977, Vol. 29, No. 4, pp. 552–583.

³ R.R. Krebs, *Narrative and the Making of US National Security*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015, p. 14.

⁴ Cf. M. Eliade, *Images and Symbols: Studies in Religious Symbolism*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1991, p. 17.

⁵ H. Tudor, *Political Myth*, London: Macmillan, 1972, p. 98; D. Elliott, “Terrorism, Global Journalism, and the Myth of the Nation State,” *Journal of Mass Media Ethics* 2004, Vol. 19, No. 1, pp. 29–45.

⁶ Cf. S. Filipowicz, *Mit i spektakl władzy*, Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, 1998, p. 7.

⁷ Cf. H. De Vriese, “Political Myth and Sacrifice,” *History of European Ideas* 2017, Vol. 43, No. 7, pp. 808–824.

⁸ *Vide*, e.g., the following literature review: S. Slaveva-Griffin, “Philosophy and Myth: A Review of Recent Scholarship,” *The European Legacy* 2007, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 247–250. *Vide etiam* W. Stoker, “Thinking through Myths: Philosophical Perspectives,” *Ars Disputandi* 2005, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 181–182.

⁹ Cf. M. Bevir, *A History of Political Science*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022, p. 1.

¹⁰ C. Bottici, “Towards a Philosophy of Political Myth,” *Iris: European Journal of Philosophy and Public Debate* 2011, Vol. 3, No. 5, pp. 31–32.

reflection and studies on the use of political myths by populists to win the hearts and minds of the people under crisis. It underlay the attempts to understand authoritarian populists' electoral successes.¹¹

Based on classic works on political myths' functions, theorists of populism direct scholarly attention to discursive practices, including nation-state-building myths, as efficient tools for addressing populists' calls for action, including sparking social mobilisation, maintaining social ties, strengthening communities, and gaining social support for unpopular political decisions.¹² At the same time, theorists of democracy point to political myths as a functional theoretical category to explore legitimacy claims democratic and anti-democratic actors, including populists, make to achieve their goals¹³ and thus stabilise political regimes.¹⁴

The current subject literature has thoroughly examined and described the nature and characteristics of nation-state-building myths¹⁵ and nation-forming ideas.¹⁶ It sheds light on the differences between myths, political myths, nation-state-building myths, and other narratives.¹⁷ Researchers have also uncovered the diversity of political myths by advancing numerous classification frameworks based on differentiated criteria.¹⁸ Those models help map political myths established and cultivated within political communities. However, operationalisable definitions and classification models contribute

¹¹ P. Norris, H.A. Garnett, M. Grömping, "The Paranoid Style of American Elections: Explaining Perceptions of Electoral Integrity in an Age of Populism," *Journal of Elections, Public Opinion and Parties* 2020, Vol. 30, No. 1, pp. 105–125; A. Molle, "Religion and Right-wing Populism in Italy: Using 'Judeo-Christian Roots' to Kill the European Union," *Religion, State & Society* 2019, Vol. 47, No. 1, pp. 151–168.

¹² M.S. Stoica, "Political Myths of the Populist Discourse," *Journal for the Study of Religions and Ideologies* 2017, Vol. 16, No. 46, pp. 63–76; C. Ungureanu, A. Popartan, "Populism as Narrative, Myth Making, and the 'Logic' of Political Emotions," *Journal of the British Academy* 2020, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 37–43.

¹³ B. Honig, "Between Decision and Deliberation: Political Paradox in Democratic Theory," *American Political Science Review* 2007, Vol. 101, No. 1, pp. 1–17; M. Canovan, "Populism for Political Theorists?," *Journal of Political Ideologies* 2004, Vol. 9, No. 3, pp. 241–252.

¹⁴ J. Gerschewski, "Legitimacy in Autocracies: Oxymoron or Essential Feature?," *Perspectives on Politics* 2018, Vol. 16, No. 3, p. 654; O. Malinova, "Framing the Collective Memory of the 1990s as a Legitimation Tool for Putin's Regime," *Problems of Post-Communism* 2021, Vol. 68, No. 5, pp. 429–441.

¹⁵ E.g., C. Bottici, A. Kühner, "Between Psychoanalysis and Political Philosophy: Towards a Critical Theory of Political Myth," *Critical Horizons* 2012, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp. 94–112.

¹⁶ E.g., A.D. Smith, *Ethno-symbolism and Nationalism. Cultural Approach*, London–New York: Routledge, 2009, p. 18; G. Schopflin, G. Hosking (eds), *Myths and Nationhood*, London–New York: Routledge, 1997; A.D. Smith, *Myths and Memories of the Nation*, New York: Oxford University Press, 1999, p. 9.

¹⁷ This article does not reconstruct the discussion on differences between the theoretical categories of myths, political myths, nation-state-building myths, ideology, and other narratives because it is beyond its research subject and goals. For the discussion, *vide e.g.*, Ch. Flood, *Political Myth...*; L. Coupe, *Myth*, London–New York: Routledge, 2009; W.G. Doty, "Mythophiles' Dyscrasia: A Comprehensive Definition of Myth," *Journal of the American Academy of Religion* 1980, Vol. 48, No. 4, pp. 531–562; B. Lincoln, *Theorizing Myth: Narrative, Ideology, and Scholarship*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1999, pp. ix–x (Preface); A. Siganos, "Definitions of Myth," *TricTrac: Journal of World Mythology and Folklore* 2008, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 68–81.

¹⁸ J. Rak, "The Typological Framework of Myths as a Tool for Studying Political Thought," *World Political Science* 2018, Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 235–256.

to our knowledge of particular discourses and social awareness.¹⁹ At the same time, the “why” question often remains unaddressed by the students of political myths. In other words, studies oriented at identifying and classifying political myths are vulnerable to failing the “so what” question test.²⁰ Usually, the “so what” question is asked by a reader to determine why a study is important, what it accounts for, and how it contributes to the knowledge in the field.²¹ Answers to the question inform why a reader should spend time learning about research findings. Accordingly, we still know little about myths’ explanatory power, which translates into their devaluation in social sciences.

This article concentrates on scholarly attempts to challenge the prevailing exploratory and descriptive approaches towards political myths. Those attempts under scrutiny consist in building explanatory frameworks involving nation-state-building myths as factors explaining other phenomena. The article scrutinises theoretical models formed to account for socially significant issues with political myths. It throws light on explanations employing nation-state-building myths to make sense of how some elements of social reality work.

Based on a critical analysis of explanatory frameworks, the article aims to identify the most relevant theoretical models treating nation-state-building myths as an explaining factor. In doing so, it reveals an explanatory potential of this theoretical category and facilitates the selection of political myths as a theoretical grounding of empirical analysis. At the same time, it shows the variety of possible ways of theorising political myths. Moreover, it aims to determine the level of their correctness and applicability to empirical studies. The article exposes the strengths and limitations of selected explanatory models. In doing so, it contributes methodologically to studies on political myths. Finally, it uncovers possible scopes and directions for developing the current models.

The remainder of the article consists of five sections. The first introduces a research design applied in further sections to evaluate explanatory frameworks. It establishes the corpus of theoretical models under analysis, puts forward research questions, and discusses criteria for the model’s critical analysis. The following three parts focus on individual explanatory frameworks. Each is examined with the same correctness and empirical applicability criteria to address the research questions. They all account for how

¹⁹ B. Bliesemann de Guevara (ed.), *Myth and Narrative in International Politics: Interpretive Approaches to the Study of IR*, London: Palgrave MacMillan, 2016; R. Bäcker, *Rosyjskie myślenie polityczne za czasów prezydenta Putina*, Toruń: Wydawnictwo Adam Marszałek, 2007, pp. 32, 37–38; R. Bäcker, “Polityczność Mitów Historycznych,” [in:] *Od teorii do praktyki politycznej. Księga jubileuszowa dedykowana Profesorowi Zbigniewowi Blokowi z okazji 40-lecia pracy naukowej i 70-lecia urodzin*, M. Kołodziejczak, R. Rosicki (eds), Poznań: Wydawnictwo Naukowe Wydziału Nauk Politycznych i Dziennikarstwa Uniwersytetu im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu, 2012, pp. 49–57.

²⁰ N. Selwyn, “So What?... A Question That Every Journal Article Needs to Answer,” *Learning, Media and Technology* 2014, Vol. 39, No. 1, pp. 1–5; R.M. Vosburgh, “Closing the Academic-Practitioner Gap: Research Must Answer the ‘SO WHAT’ Question,” *Human Resource Management Review* 2022, Vol. 32, No. 1, pp. 1–11.

²¹ J.M. McCarthy, T.N. Bauer, D.M. Truxillo, N.R. Anderson, A.C. Costa, S.M. Ahmed, “Applicant Perspectives During Selection: A Review Addressing ‘So what?’, ‘What’s new?’, and ‘Where to next?’,” *Journal of Management* 2017, Vol. 43, No. 6, pp. 1693–1725.

selected narratives resonate with nation-state-building myths. The first advances the causal relationships between external strategic narratives and political myths. Then, the discussion goes on to the possible explanation for the populist surge. It also engages with a broader debate about the efficiency of legitimacy claims. The third explanatory framework under scrutiny looks at the mobilising potential of political myths to tackle the question of reasons for people taking to the streets. The article finishes with a discussion and suggestions regarding avenues for future research.

Research Design

The corpus of theoretical models under analysis includes the explicitly determined explanatory frameworks that treat nation-state-building myths as an explaining factor. The approaches covering only empirical observations and lacking generalisation and theorising are omitted. Similarly, descriptions of cases without methodological assumptions and theoretical grounding, even if resulting in cause-and-effect discussions, are beyond the scope of scrutiny. Apart from the subject and formal criteria, their inclusion in the corpus results from being disseminated throughout a paper indexed on Google Scholar and has been empirically tested by at least one researcher or a research team.

The above criteria for selecting explanatory schemes do not depreciate other analytically effective approaches. Above all, they aim to set the most advanced theoretical propositions to provide a theoretical grounding for empirical research. Compared to others, they require relatively minor modifications in terms of correctness and analytical applicability before being used as a theoretical tool.

The critical analysis of the sources, including the existing models, relies on Joanna Rak's analytical tool for analysing explanatory frameworks. It revolves around three research problems that translate into questions. The first problem is what explanatory models, according to the existing subject literature, treat nation-state-building myths as an explaining factor. It frames the following question: what do political myths explain? The quest to tackle the question draws upon the assumption that "political beings, phenomena, processes, their configuration, or lack thereof are the explananda which are explicated through their explanans."²² Simply speaking, an explanandum is a sentence describing something to be explained. The explanans is nation-state-building myths since they account for an explanandum. The analysis delves into theoretical models that consider nation-state-building myths an explaining factor. It organises models in subject order to determine the spectrum of nation-state-building myths usage to account for events or properties. Then, it defines the types of explanatory frameworks offered in the subject literature.

The second research problem is the identified models' correctness. Therefore, a research question delves into the structures of the explananda. It asks what follows: to what

²² J. Rak, *Theorizing Cultures of Political Violence in Times of Austerity: Studying Social Movements in Comparative Perspective*, London–New York: Routledge, 2018, p. 39.

extent are explanatory frameworks formulated correctly? Addressing the research question has the form of a test. The latter draws upon checking whether, and if yes, to what extent, explanatory frameworks meet correctness criteria. The set of criteria includes the following requirements: (1) it establishes a cause-and-effect relationship between an explaining factor, and a factor to be explained with the general sentences, which may be conveyed in the form of the zero or the first conditional sentences and their apodosis (the consequence) involves the sentence intimating the emergence of an explained factor or presenting a property being explained; (2) it covers the individual sentences which state that the events designated by a protasis or protases (the condition[s])²³ of general sentences appeared; (3) it is operationalisable and thus verifiable; (4) it is not value-laden; (5) it is not normative; (6) it does not offer the statements in the shape of the second, the third, and the mixed conditional (a mixture of the second and the third conditionals) sentences; and (7) it is internally consistent. The general rule is that the larger the extent of the criteria fulfilment by an explanatory framework is, the bigger the extent of its correctness is.²⁴

Finally, the last research problem is the identified frameworks' scope of applicability to investigate the social realm. Accordingly, the third research question relates to the applicability of explanatory frameworks to empirical analysis. It is as follows: what is the extent of the identified explanatory models' applicability to empirical studies? A highly applicable model should allow a researcher to explain a relatively broad range of beings, phenomena, and processes. It also ought to be useful to account for which phenomenon from a particular class of phenomena emerges as a result of the emergence of other phenomena.²⁵ Engaging with the results of the analysis of models' correctness, the study examines whether and under what conditions they apply to generate new knowledge in the field intersubjectively. Besides, it sheds light on characteristics of the research fields that can be explored with models. In general, the more specific and detailed the presentation of the causal relations between an explaining factor (nation-state-building myths) and an issue to be explained, providing the possibility of high accuracy and precision of explanation, the larger the extent of the applicability of the model is.²⁶ In addition, the broader the range of the application of a framework is, the more informative it is.²⁷

Summing up, the three research questions structure and inform the critical analysis of Google Scholar records, i.e., papers offering explanatory frameworks that meet the selection criteria. The following sections introduce the identified theoretical models and deliver research findings concerning their correctness and applicability to empirical studies.

²³ S. Nowak, *Metodologia badań społecznych*, Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, 2007, p. 352.

²⁴ J. Rak, *Theorizing Cultures...*, p. 39.

²⁵ K.-D. Opp, *Theories of Political Protest and Social Movements: A Multidisciplinary Introduction, Critique, and Synthesis*, London–New York: Routledge, 2009, p. 24.

²⁶ M. Risjord, "Reasons, Causes, and Action Explanation," *Philosophy of the Social Sciences* 2005, Vol. 35, No. 3, pp. 294–306.

²⁷ K.-D. Opp, *Theories of Political Protest...*, p. 25.

External Strategic Narratives and Nation-State-Building Myths

Contributing to the study of international politics and security, the first explanatory framework applies to account for why strategic narratives are effective.²⁸ It focuses on constructing political discourse through the interaction between political myths and strategic narratives used by external actors to influence a political community.²⁹ Olivier Schmitt discovered a theoretical gap in research on strategic narratives, which was an unresolved research problem about how the targeted political communities receive strategic narratives and how the latter is probable to have a political impact on the communities, i.e., shape the local socio-political debates and results of political decision-making processes. Inspired by this puzzle, Schmitt goes into the details of the current generalisation that the efficiency of strategic narratives depends on their match with society's cultural context.³⁰ The following premise followed it: "appeal to the values, interest and prejudices in a target audience"³¹ is through a community's political myths. Accordingly, the latter explains a strategic narrative's reception and acceptance within political communities.³²

Building on a single case study of the reception of the Russian strategic narratives on the political debate in France, Schmitt argues that political myths are a factor that explains how strategic narratives are received.³³ According to Schmitt's model, "the degree to which an external strategic narrative resonates with local political myths determines the effectiveness and impact of the strategic narrative."³⁴ When an ontological status of an explaining factor and a factor to be explained is concerned, both political myths and strategic narratives are narratives describing the story of a succession of events.³⁵

Schmitt's internally coherent theoretical approach establishes a cause-and-effect relationship between an explaining factor and a factor to be explained with the general sentences. Nevertheless, the formulation of the relationships causes the first application difficulties. It is due to the researcher's use of normative and value-laden phrases such as "must" and "has to" instead of the first or zero conditional sentences establishing the variants of possible relationships.

However, a note should be taken that Schmitt's explanatory framework draws on a set of assumptions that can be inferred from normative sentences. First, Schmitt determines a condition of "some similarity between the strategic narrative and the political myth in

²⁸ C. van Noort, T. Colley, "How Do Strategic Narratives Shape Policy Adoption? Responses to China's Belt and Road Initiative," *Review of International Studies* 2021, Vol. 47, No. 1, pp. 39–63.

²⁹ O. Schmitt, "When are Strategic Narratives Effective? The Shaping of Political Discourse through the Interaction Between Political Myths and Strategic Narratives," *Contemporary Security Policy* 2018, Vol. 39, No. 4, p. 487.

³⁰ R. Stryker, "Beyond History Versus Theory: Strategic Narrative and Sociological Explanation," *Sociological Methods & Research* 1996, Vol. 24, No. 3, p. 304.

³¹ J. Gow, B. Wilkinson, "Conclusion," [in:] *The Art of Creating Power. Freedman on Strategy*, B. Wilkinson, J. Gow (eds), London: Hurst, 2017, p. 377.

³² O. Schmitt, "When are Strategic Narratives Effective?"..., p. 490.

³³ *Ibidem*, p. 488.

³⁴ *Ibidem*.

³⁵ *Ibidem*.

terms of their content³⁶ for the external strategic narrative to be efficient. The strategic narrative resonates with a local political myth if the story being told is about similar themes. Second, the actors-events-plot-time-setting-space structure of the strategic narrative resonates with a local political myth if they share the narrative aspect. The efficiency of resonating results from the strategic narrative's potential to fall into the myth and actualise its structure.³⁷

As Schmitt emphasises, each community fosters numerous political myths that potentially vary and may contradict each other. Looking at political myths as a heterogeneous phenomenon, Schmitt advances a typology based on the degree of myths' universality (universal and local myths) and coherence with other myths (cohesive and contradictory myths).³⁸

Let us delve into the typology's details. Schmitt points to the dispersion of political myths and their coherence with other myths. The former feature covers the degree to which a significant number of various political communities can approve of a given political myth. While a universal myth has considerable potential for dispersion due to being widely accepted by numerous different communities across the world, local myths, especially nationalist ones, are shared within limited groups of people. In turn, the degree of coherence indicates a myth's potential to accommodate or clash with others. It covers the content of a narrative structure that overlaps with political myths existing within a community.³⁹

Schmitt illustrates these four types of myths with examples but does not introduce any research tools to measure them. The same disclaimer applies to the status of the external strategic narratives which have been described and not subjected to intersubjective measurement. It reduces the explanatory framework's applicability to empirical research. Although the case study omits operationalisation, the theoretical categories included in the model can be successfully operationalised and verified.

Furthermore, the typology consists of two dyads of political myths distinguished by different and clearly determined criteria. Nonetheless, if their operational definitions were proposed, it would still only be possible to look at political myths dichotomously. The extreme features that characterise all four types of political myths are gradual. The construction of continuums to measure these features among the exemplifications of myths would contribute to the development of Schmitt's theoretical model. These scales should include subtypes of four types to identify variations in myths and to pinpoint variants of the reasons for reception and acceptance of the external strategic narratives.

The values taken on by the myths present in a political community result in the effectiveness of the reception of strategic narratives. More specifically, the reception and the possible influence of a strategic narrative result from a myth's positioning along those two dimensions. The direction of relationships between the explained and explaining

³⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 492.

³⁷ *Ibidem*.

³⁸ *Ibidem*.

³⁹ *Ibidem*.

factors is as follows. Suppose an external strategic narrative falls into the narrative pattern of a local political myth. In that case, local politicians gain extra rhetorical resources to promote the desired policy by adopting the structure or content of the external strategic narrative and adjusting it to the local political context. As Schmitt emphasises, it is how the politicians update the local political myth and advance an external subject's perspective.⁴⁰

Schmitt's explanatory framework applies to compare and evaluate the diverse influence strategic narratives have on different political communities. The author argues that myths are not fixed, but their structure, content, and diffusion modes undergo reinterpretation and actualisation. Such "work on myths" is based on updating and modifying myths to provide significance and maintain their function and status as interpretative lenses.⁴¹ Nevertheless, political myths are relatively persistent, and their substantial change is long-term.⁴² Thus, if the level of effectiveness of strategic narratives changes while the myths remain the same, the model is not applicable to explain the dynamics of change.

At the same time, Schmitt's study avoids taking into account the control variables. It cannot be ruled out that the characteristics of the social, cultural, economic, or political context at the time of reception of the external strategic narrative were not more significant than political myths. The cause-effect relationship placed in the theoretical model is, therefore, worth revising in terms of the significance of the broad and changing context.

What is more, the framework omits under what conditions the relationships between the external strategic narratives and political myths emerge. It remains a puzzle whether a type of political subject or who produces, disseminates, or mediates in dissemination influences the efficiency of discursive efforts. The single case study devoted to the Russian strategic narratives does not allow us to infer whether the same narratives distributed by other subjects have the same political impact.

In sum, Schmitt's explanatory framework meets most of the correctness criteria and is highly applicable to empirical studies. After several modifications and developments, it may be an analytically efficient theoretical tool under the discussed conditions. At the same time, one should remember that the causal relation draws on a limited single case study. Although it is of theory-generation value, it requires in-depth comparative analysis to contribute to our understanding of when the external narratives are efficient. The knowledge of the mechanism may be crucial for the discussion on why some meddlers and their hybrid interference are efficient and undermine democracy, whereas others are not.⁴³ It may contribute to securing the channels of cognitive influence used by external and internal political actors to impact election results.

⁴⁰ *Ibidem.*

⁴¹ *Ibidem*, p. 491.

⁴² T. Apolte, J. Müller, "The Persistence of Political Myths and Ideologies," *European Journal of Political Economy* 2022, Vol. 71, p. 3.

⁴³ Cf. M. Wigell, "Hybrid Interference as a Wedge Strategy: A Theory of External Interference in Liberal Democracy," *International Affairs* 2019, Vol. 95, No. 2, pp. 255–275.

The Populist Surge and Nation-State-Building Myths

Drawing on the political science literature that emerged after the great economic crisis of 2007–2008, Mihnea S. Stoica points to the relationships between the populist surge and nation-state-building myths. As Stoica argues, individuals and groups who undergo crises are more prone to search for symbolic justifications and explanations for the situation they are experiencing. It leads to the assumption that populists that provide such reasons and explanations in the form of nation-state-building myths are likely to win electoral support during a crisis.⁴⁴ This mechanism accounts for the populist surge after the mentioned crisis.⁴⁵ However, recent studies embedded theoretically in Stoica's explanatory framework deliver convincing empirical evidence to confirm its applicability to explain the populist surge, electoral successes, and efficiency of legitimacy claims also during other crises,⁴⁶ including the global public health crisis.⁴⁷ They contribute empirically and theoretically to the verification of Stoica's explanatory framework.

Stoica builds upon Raoul Girardet's typology of political myths that covers the variants of discursive myth-driven legitimisation, i.e., the modes of gaining political legitimacy. Girardet's typology differentiates between conspiracy, golden age, saviour, and unity myths. The conspiracy myth depicts a specific group of people who endeavour to disrupt the status quo for individual benefits. A particular state of emergency results in the need for saving, which lays the ground for the saviour myth. Due to their intrinsic enthusiasm and knowledge, the saviour can restore socially desired order. However, a crisis also sparks the desire for a better future, addressed through the golden age myth. The latter entails a rejection of the contemporary world. In lieu of the unacceptable political reality, it presents a utopian state of prosperity, peace, harmony, and political stability. The unity myth involves organising individuals into a collective subject, usually a political community free of internal conflicts.⁴⁸

Notably, Stoica operationalises the theoretical categories included in Girardet's typology and determines theoretical links between them. The author contributes methodologically to the field by creating a tool for analysing populist discourses. Moreover, Stoica uses them to advance an explanatory framework.

⁴⁴ Cf. S. Frunză, "Political Communication and the Median Space of Religious Experience," *Revista de cercetare și intervenție socială* 2012, Vol. 39, p. 183; O. Onopko, L. Landik, "Political Myths in Election Campaigns: Structure, Functions, Types," *Historia Provinciae – The Journal of Regional History* 2018, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 50–86; J. Charteris-Black, "Britain as a Container: Immigration Metaphors in the 2005 Election Campaign," *Discourse & Society* 2006, Vol. 17, No. 5, pp. 563–581.

⁴⁵ M.S. Stoica, "Political Myths"..., p. 66.

⁴⁶ *Vide*, e.g., P.S. Sawyer, "Conspiracism in Populist Radical Right Candidates: Rallying the Base or Mainstreaming the Fringe?," *International Journal of Politics, Culture, and Society* 2022, Vol. 35, No. 3, pp. 305–340; R.N. Khoudary, "Populist Strategies in the Political Advertising Discourse of the French National Front," *REiLA: Journal of Research and Innovation in Language* 2021, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 146–158.

⁴⁷ *Vide*, e.g., J. Rak, "Quasi-Militant Democracy as a New Form of Sacred in Poland During the Corona Crisis," *Journal for the Study of Religions and Ideologies* 2020, Vol. 19, No. 57, pp. 111–128; P. Oskolkov, "Holistic Myth and Populist Reality: Populism, Nativism and Biopolitics in Times of Pandemics," *Interdisciplinary Journal of Populism* 2020, Vol. 3, pp. 7–15.

⁴⁸ R. Girardet, *Mythes et mythologies politiques*, Paris: Editions du Seuil, 1986.

Stoica's model is free of value-laden and normative assumptions. Instead, it hierarchises political myths based on their social significance and perceives the conspiracy myth as a core for populist discourse. It results from populists' presentations of the world as an uncertain and insecure place where society is endangered by "the others." While society is sacred, "the others" are diabolised. The former is established on well-known and widely accepted rules; the latter denies their validity and is unpredictable and dangerous. At the same time, the conspiracy myth has a political impact only if co-emerges with the remaining three myths. The saviour myth describes the populist leader or party as being able to save the world, restore solidarity within endangered societies, and spot and tackle the problems of their supporters or followers. Finally, the unity myth draws on and produces a feeling of symbolic empowerment. It helps the majority become the people, a major category in the populists' rhetoric. In populist imaginary, the united people are a group that engages all or most of those disappointed or unhappy with the status quo. The people have an ultimate objective defined within the golden age myth. The present is a period between the golden age and the "revenge of times."⁴⁹

Simultaneously, Stoica goes a step further in determining political myths' explanatory potential in studies on populism. As Stoica highlights, the four types of political myths covered by Girardet's classification framework emerge within the political discourse linked to a plethora of ideological identities. Nevertheless, Stoica's work reveals that political myths also occur in the discourse of political movements even though they do not have a solid ideological foundation.⁵⁰

Using political myths can be populists' well-established strategy or unconscious communicational behaviour. However, regardless of an awareness factor, Stoica's model draws on the premise that "The void generated by the lack of ideological substance is filled with stories rooted in political mythology, depicting characters with memorable and strongly opposed features ("good" versus "bad," "us" versus "them" etc.) as a means of simplifying the messages and of reaching out to all of those dissatisfied with the political process or simply uninterested in understanding the complexity of it."⁵¹ According to Stoica, a political actor, either individual or collective, can make use of the void to meet their own political interest and benefit from the need for symbolic justifications and explanations for the situation spread within a community.

In Stoica's model, the relationship between the explaining factor and the factor to be explained is as follows: if political actors contrive to address political myths spread within a targeted political community and draw upon them legitimacy claims, they will successfully generate legitimacy.⁵² To put it in another way, when the content of political myths distributed in public discourse by populists or other actors seeking public support is coherent with political myths established and cultivated within a political community, the actor is likely to be supported by the community. Importantly, Stoica's explanatory framework is internally consistent. It determines a cause-and-effect relationship between

⁴⁹ M.S. Stoica, "Political Myths"..., pp. 71–72.

⁵⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 70.

⁵¹ *Ibidem*, p. 72.

⁵² *Ibidem*.

the factors with the general sentences, which may be conveyed in the form of the zero and the first conditional sentences. Their apodosis (the consequence) involves the sentence intimating the emergence of an explained factor or presenting a property being explained. In addition, it covers the individual sentences, which state that the events designated by a protasis of general sentences appeared.

The causal relationship established by Stoica suggests that political myths firmly established in the community result in the susceptibility to their use to manage the community. This explanatory framework has a much more comprehensive range of applications than just explaining the election successes of populists worldwide and the populist surge. Most importantly, it can explain the failures of democratic actors who often base their arguments on rationale rather than political myths.

At the same time, the explanatory model applies to comprehend why some legitimacy claims are efficient while others fail. It results from Stoica's precise determination of the degree of the myths' coherence as a factor translating into the impact legitimacy claims have on building legitimacy. This suggestion is of growing importance in times of crisis when public institutions lose public trust and seek to restore it with intense communication efforts and actions.⁵³

Finally, the model can be used to predict the consequences of using different narratives, i.e., the influence of political myths on the political behaviour of a community. Knowledge of the content, mutual relationships between myths, and their structure is necessary to predict the political decisions of a community, which are reactions to the narratives present in the political discourse.

To summarise, Stoica's explanatory framework meets all correctness criteria and is highly applicable to empirical studies. Its explanatory potential can translate into contributions to works on populism, contemporary political regimes' vulnerability to populist threats, stabilising political systems through legitimacy claims, and the efficiency of legitimacy claims.

Mobilisation and Nation-State-Building Myths

An important theoretical contribution to the scholarly literature on the explanatory power of political myths is Chiara Bottici's seminal work on their mobilising potential. However, a note should be taken here that this work arises from and is intellectually anchored in philosophy and not social sciences. Bottici argues that political myths lie behind efficiently calling groups of people for action based on the myths' performative and moral dimensions.⁵⁴ The Bottici approach needs to provide details of the dimensions' definitions and potential measurements to apply to contentious politics and social

⁵³ *Vide*, e.g., L. Ralph, "The Dynamic Nature of Police Legitimacy on Social Media," *Policing and Society* 2022, Vol. 32, No. 7, pp. 817–831; M.D. Bonner, L. Dammert, "Constructing Police Legitimacy During Protests: Frames and Consequences for Human Rights," *Policing and Society* 2022, Vol. 32, No. 5, pp. 629–645.

⁵⁴ C. Bottici, *A Philosophy of Political Myth*, New York: Cambridge University Press, 2007, p. 3.

movement studies. Although it meets all the correctness criteria, its applicability to social science empirical research is limited.

Bottici's explanatory framework avoids answering the questions of when and under what conditions some or all nation-state-building myths have a political impact reflected in mass mobilisation. It also remains silent about the political myths' structure and content. In its current form, the model can inspire and paves a way of thinking about explaining mobilisation, but it requires development to apply to social science empirical research. At the same time, the advocates of Bottici's approach should consider other explanatory frameworks and revise configurations of and relationships between factors accounting for social mobilisation. Treating political myths as the only or major explaining factor may result in oversimplification of complex reasons behind taking to the streets.

Noteworthy, Bottici's approach is utilised and developed on the grounds of social sciences. However, resting on or referring to political myths is not considered sufficient for mass mobilisation. Ariel C. Armony and Victor Armony are far from overestimating the role of nation-state-building myths in social mobilisation. Drawing upon the case study of the Argentinian wave of protest in the 1990s and early 2000s, they discuss the significance of political myths in the context of other factors explaining collective action.⁵⁵ Although the discussion and the resulting explanatory framework are context-specific and context-driven, the conclusion offers some generalisations derived from empirical observations. As Armony and Armony underline, the current explanations range from political actors' choices to their subjective aims. They determine a frame for collective action. In other words, to comprehend the reason for taking to the streets, researchers account for what made protesters angry. Simultaneously, Armony and Armony suggest supplementing this approach with insight into the context of enduring conceptions of national identity and their interaction with political and economic factors.⁵⁶

Thus, Armony and Armony draw scholarly attention to the significance of perceptions and beliefs interpreted as both subjectively constructed and objectively formed by institutions and public discourse, even if they are contradictory to reality. Moreover, the maintenance of the myth can steer people towards manifesting specific attitudes and managing their emotions. As Armony and Armony argue, the demands of citizens challenging an existing political and social situation are in line with collective notions of their potential as a nation, at least to some extent.⁵⁷ At the same time, the status of the extent remains an open question. This cultural framework largely relies on shared nation-state-building myths next to memories and dreams.⁵⁸ Nonetheless, the authors remain silent about the relationships and differences between myths, memories, and dreams.

According to Armony and Armony, myths are enduring and embedded in national identity. Simultaneously, they undergo cyclical revivals and latency correlated to

⁵⁵ A.C. Armony, V. Armony, "Indictments, Myths, and Citizen Mobilization in Argentina: A Discourse Analysis," *Latin American Politics and Society* 2005, Vol. 47, No. 4, p. 27.

⁵⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 47.

⁵⁷ *Ibidem*.

⁵⁸ *Ibidem*.

economic, political, and social trends. The following statement illustrates this premise: “With the myth of national success in the background – a myth that experiences surges and decays – it is possible to understand why Argentinians were ready to trust politicians again as the unprecedented crisis subsided. Indeed, it would seem that many Argentinians still expect – perhaps now more than ever – that the promise of a Great Argentina will finally come true.”⁵⁹ The approach meets most of the correctness criteria. However, there is a caveat related to the model’s internal consistency. It omits the difference between gaining trust, generating legitimacy, and triggering mass mobilisation based on nation-state-building myths. As a result, legitimacy may be mistaken for mobilisation. It makes a cause-and-effect relationship between an explaining factor and a factor to be explained unclearly. There is no differentiation between how the potential of political myths is activated to evoke what reaction. Moreover, the correlation’s nature needs to be more specific. These issues reduce the framework’s applicability to empirical research but determine directions for its further development.

To sum up, Bottici’s and Armony and Armony’s explanatory frameworks fulfil all or most correctness criteria, respectively. However, their applicability to empirical studies is limited since they do not allow researchers to account for various phenomena that resonate with political myths. They also avoid getting us closer to understanding which phenomenon from a particular class of phenomena emerges as a result of the emergence of other phenomena. These remarks also apply to other endeavours to establish relationships between social mobilisation and political myths.

Notably, the growing body of research devoted to social mobilisation, especially contentious politics and social movement studies, could benefit from explanatory frameworks, including the theoretical category of political myths and myth-related factors. Nonetheless, those models require further development to deliver a plausible explanation for the role of nation-state-building myths in triggering mass mobilisation. Above all, it is necessary to explain in what situations the consequence of using narratives rooted in the semantic structures of political myths is obtaining legitimation and in which it is sparking collective action.

Discussion and Conclusions

The existing explanatory models treat political communities as homogeneous in terms of the cultivation and distribution of political myths. Thus, the importance of content, the degree of cultivation, and distribution patterns remain unknown for political narratives’ resonating processes. It is one of the most important directions in developing explanatory models using the theoretical category of political myth.

The subject literature on nation-state-building myths often offers idiographic but rarely nomothetic approaches. Attempts to generalise individual empirical observations are somewhat scattered, and an integrated approach to them is still needed to enrich the knowledge of political myth-driven mechanisms. Nevertheless, some current case

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 50.

studies focused on political myths as an explanatory factor have significant theory-generating potential. They lay the groundwork for a theory explaining how and why certain narratives or discursive frames resonate with political myths effectively. At the same time, they pose both theory-verification and theory-generation challenges to researchers of political thought, social movements, contentious politics, social mobilisation, political discourse, international relations, security studies, democratic theory, and political theorists in general.

Among empirical studies on nation-state-building myths, works in which only one, an explained or explaining factor is measured, and the other is taken for granted, prevail. Static approaches dominate over dynamic perspectives. Furthermore, researchers offer intuitive explanations of the role and significance of political myths in a community's political decision-making. Such an approach reduces the possibility of identifying the structure and direction of relationships between the factors. A more comprehensive analytical approach has to be taken to see political myths in the bigger picture.

Moreover, several existing theoretical models go beyond the description of cases and can be the basis of comprehensive comparative studies. In such studies, it is worth remembering the possibilities of diversifying and triangulating research techniques to minimise the risk of errors in interpreting sources. The major techniques employed by the students of political myths are content analysis,⁶⁰ discourse analysis,⁶¹ and critical discourse analysis.⁶² Much less frequent are thematic analyses (sometimes triangulated with content analysis)⁶³ or frame analysis (also called framing analysis; sometimes triangulated with discourse analysis),⁶⁴ allowing for an in-depth analysis of narratives.

⁶⁰ Vide, e.g., D.-M. Pitigoi, "Political Myths in the Context of Political Symbolism: A Case Study on the Social Media Discourses of Three Romanian Politicians," *Perspective Politice* 2021, Vol. 14, No. 1–2, pp. 87–104; H. Dyrhaage, "Political Myths in Climate Leadership: The Case of Danish Climate and Energy Pioneering," *Scandinavian Political Studies* 2021, Vol. 44, No. 1, pp. 13–33.

⁶¹ Vide, e.g., A. Dălălău, "Building Legitimacy: The Role of Political Myths in the Presidential Campaigns of the Early 90s in Romania," *Politikon: The IAPSS Journal of Political Science* 2021, Vol. 51, pp. 17–32; K. Lynggaard, "Exploring the Emotional Appeal of Green and Social Europe Myths Among Pan-European Union Organizations," *Journal of European Public Policy* 2017, Vol. 24, No. 10, pp. 1409–1429.

⁶² Vide, e.g., A. Panay, "fear appeal construction in the Daily Mail Online: A critical discourse analysis of 'Prime Minister Corbyn and the 1000 Days that Destroyed Britain'," *Critical Approaches to Discourse Analysis Across Disciplines (CADAAD)* 2017, Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 45–62; J. Wygnańska, "Between Political Myths, Dormant Resentments, and Redefinition of the Recent History: A Case Study of Serbian National Identity," *Qualitative Sociology Review* 2021, Vol. 17, No. 2, pp. 38–68.

⁶³ Vide, e.g., L. Zhong, J. Zhang, "Political Myth as Strategic Communication: Analysis of Chinese Dream's Rhetoric and English News Media's Interpretation," *International Journal of Strategic Communication* 2016, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 51–68. For an example of the triangulation of content and thematic analysis vide, e.g., J. Rak, P. Osiewicz, "The Populist Response to the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Comparative Analysis of the Positions of Duda and Fernández," *Serbian Political Thought* 2021, Vol. 74, No. 4, pp. 5–32.

⁶⁴ Vide, i.a., S. Akopov, C. Aslanyan, L. Boliatchevets, P. Slusarchuk, "Is 'E' for 'EMPIRE'? Re-imagining New Russian Identity Through Symbolic Politics of 'Sochi-2014'," *Russian Journal of Communication* 2017, Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 1–18. For an example of the triangulation of frame and discourse analysis vide, e.g., A. Ljubojević, "Remembering the Hague: The Impact of International Criminal Justice on Memory Practices in Croatia," [in:] *Framing the Nation and Collective Identities: Political Rituals and Cultural Memory of the Twentieth-Century Traumas in Croatia*, V. Pavlaković, D. Pauković (eds), London–New York: Routledge, 2019, pp. 177–193.

Each technique offers specific research procedures that entail opportunities and burdens for analysing data. The basis for selecting a technique must be knowledge of sources and clearly defined research goals.

Besides, the study of very responses to external strategic narratives, legitimacy claims, and other narratives aimed at generating social reactions also requires conducting surveys. They are necessary to identify the deep structures of political thinking in the form of political myths.

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